

Challenges Faced by International Students in China

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to identify the problems among international students in China. Questionnaires were sent to 100 international students at Inner Mongolia University, Agriculture University, Inner Mongolia Normal University, and Inner Mongolia University of economic and finance which had been selected based on multi sampling. During the study abroad by international students adjustment problems experienced by doctorate, post graduate, undergraduate students in Inner Mongolia Province China. Mooney Problem Check List (MPCL) was used to recognize the categories of problems among international students in China. This research survey consists of 11 categories of problems. The categories included health, finances, lifestyle and career, social and recreational, psychological social relation, personal relationships and emotional problems, marriage and sexual, family, moral and religious, adapting to academic work, future career adapting, curriculum and method of teaching problems. Suggestions and recommendations were also collected through interviews. Data collected were analyzed using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS). Pareto Principle was used to identify the most disturbing items in each category of problems. The Major finding of this research shows that the most disturbing categories of problems among international students at China, Inner Mongolia province are social and recreational problems and curriculum and method of teaching problems.

INTRODUCTION

Higher education is an improving issue in China. Presenting new courses and programs in universities, increasing the number of universities and accepting higher numbers of students each year in Chinese universities shows the importance of education in China.

Most of the students, who want to have higher education usually, choose United State of America, Canada, Australia, Germany, New Zealand, Turkey, United Kingdom, and other European countries(新闻中心, 2017). The leading cause of those countries to be chosen are better condition of the education level if compared to student's homeland, cultural diversity, and wide range of educational opportunities for students. In addition to this, according to a report of it is known that students who go abroad for the education contribute to the economy. In this way, both students and the countries where they have been for study, that give education have mutual advantages (Roslyn kunin and associates Inc. 2009).

With the development of China, international student's education in China grows like mushrooms shoots after a spring rain. More and more international

students are rushing into China to learn Chinese and its culture. The number of students of different nationalities can be seen as witnesses to show that China is extremely conducive to studying and sharing knowledge.

The number of international students who come to China for the purpose of higher education studies from different countries and the different cultures of the world are increasing day by day. Most of the students come from Central Asian States, Africa, India, Russia, Pakistan, Mongolia, Nepal, Aswan (The association of south east Asian Nations), and many students come from America, England, and Europe.

According to statistics, in 2016 from 205 countries and from different regions 442,773 foreign students came to china at 31 provinces, autonomous regions and municipalities of 829 colleges and universities, research institutes and other teaching institutions for higher studies. In year 2017 number of international students increased by 45,13. The growth rate of 11.35% (the below data are excluding Hong Kong, Macao and Taiwan regions)(中华人民共和国教育部官网, 2017).

Graph 1: year by Year change in International students 2016-2017

The number of international students in the people republic of china in 2016-2017 reached an all time high of 610,000 reflecting an 11% increase in student enrollment in various graduate level disciplines(中华人民共和国教育部官网, 2017).

In China ranked by country, 15,540 from Korea, 23,838 from the United States, 23,044 from the United States, 18,644 from Thailand, 18,626 from Pakistan, 18,717 from India, 17,971 from Russia, 14,714 from Indonesia, 13,996 from Kazakhstan, 13,595 from Japan, 10,639 from Vietnam, 10,414 from France, 9,907

students from Laos, 8,508 from Mongolia, 8,145 from Germany, 6,880 from Malaysia 5440 students from Africa. According to the Student selection and Placement centers and Chinese government scholarship centers gender distribution data, male students are higher than female students. The above mention situation which can be considered as gender discrimination, gives information about the cultural background of international students who come to China for higher education(中华人民共和国教育部官网, 2017).

Graph 2: Number of international student (2017) in China from different countries

International students in the People Republic of China often encounter difficulties in adjusting their new but different culture environment. International students come to China with different worldviews, different culture, and different linguistics backgrounds. International students make up a significant proportion of students in China's higher education and have received increasing attention in the past years. The increase in international student's enrollment has changed the demographics of student's population on many Chinese campuses and challenged Chinese Education authority to rethink students learning and teaching in higher education. International students, particularly those who enrolled in master and doctoral programs are important contributions in many fields of study, such as management sciences, engineering, biology, science, medicine, and information technology. They are not only contributing to research activities in these field, but also serve as teaching assistants for various undergraduate courses and laboratory sections. Many students experience linguistic and cultural challenges different from those of local students. They often struggle with academic language in Chinese. Furthermore to interact socially with Chinese peers, instructor, and local community members, international students have to personally adjust to local Chinese culture.

When the homeland of the students which choose China is analyzed, higher number of students come from Europe, United State of America, Africa, South Asia, (Pakistan and India, Bangladesh), Central Asia (Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan,) Russia, Mongolia, and Laos.

Educational Scholarship in China for International students

Scholarships, which can be determined as the most important service to be distributed to international students, are distributed as scholarship under the government, Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS) and The World Academy of Sciences (TWAS), Provisional government, institute, entrusted by the Ministry of Education of the People's Republic of China (hereinafter referred to as MOE), is responsible for the enrollment and the administration of Chinese Government Scholarship programs. Now, 289 designated Chinese universities offer a wide variety of academic programs in science, engineering, agriculture, medicine, economics, legal studies, management, education, history, literature, philosophy, and fine arts for scholarship recipients at all levels. which are provided by the ministries and intuitions, scholarships of some private foundations and associations(新闻中心, 2018).

There are many scholarships and funding distributed by the Chinese government, such as Marine Scholarship of China, Chinese Government Scholarship, (hereinafter referred to as CSC) local Government Scholarship, Chinese Government Scholarship-Bilateral Program, Confucius Institute Scholarship, school/University scholarship, and enterprise scholarship.

There are other services to be distributed by the Chinese government, such as Prime ministry abroad China and culture Chairmanship(新闻中心, 2018).

In order to promote the mutual understanding, cooperation and exchanges in various fields between China and other countries, the Chinese government has

set up a series of scholarship programs to sponsor international students, teachers and scholars to study and conduct research in Chinese universities.

In People republic of China, number of international students is over then 450000 on scholarship. This includes full or partial scholarships in accordance with the educational exchange agreements or consensus between the Chinese government and governments of other countries, institutions, universities or international organizations. It supports undergraduate students, graduate students, general scholars and senior scholars.

There is no record data about the universities, foundation and association scholarships. In the context of these scholarships above mentioned tuition fee, language fee, health insurance, residence and monthly allowance which are provided to international students yearly.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Even though international students pay attention, during the selection process of admission, to the cultural harmony and countries closeness, it is possible for them to have compliance issues, leading cause of compliance issues which lead to cultural shock and stress are language inadequacy, psychological problems, exposure to discrimination and economic difficulties. These problems may get denser with the addition of bigger difference between students social environment at their homeland and host country china.

Foreign scholars Research

International students face problems in different areas. Problems in the field of language, finance, social, psychological, health, recreational and academic are seen as common problems among international students (Andrade, 2006). Based on Hus (2003), international students' problems are career choices, language problems, and homesickness, and cultural adjustment, relationship, self-esteem and discrimination issues (Hus, 2003). Social interaction and communication problems, social connectedness, social support, language barriers, homesickness, academic, financial are the common difficulties among Chinese international students in United States (Lui, 2009a; Yeh, 2009). The experiences of international students highlight problems in the field of health and finances insurance, adapting to a new culture and homesickness, lack of understanding from the broader university community and of the English language. Spoken language barriers are more common than written language problems among international students. Many international students feel that people at the university do not understand their culture (Billikopf, 2009; Sherry, 2010). The differences between cultures may lead to experiences of interpersonal and intrapersonal conflicts among international students. Therefore, international students

must find a balance between two cultures (Lin, 1997). High social connectedness among international students lead to less psychological stress and an easier adjustment to the new social environment (Lui, 2009b). In addition, the loss of a social support system among international students can have a significant negative influence on the psychological well-being of students, including depression and loneliness. International students tend to feel a deep sense of loss in moving to another country after leaving friends and families (Lui, 2009b) and psychological stressors such as changing in support system may lead to social isolation (Lin, 1997). Fluency in the Chinese language play highlight role in academic classes as students feel comfortable in articulating their knowledge on essay exams, in classrooms or in research papers. In contrast, international students with a low level of fluency in Chinese have negative affects their psychological well-being, and these students may not eligible to receive teaching assistantships in universities or other facilities (Lin, 1997) Homesickness is another important stressor issue that international students face. They often miss their family, friends or their ethnic cuisine and they daydream of memories back home (Lin, 1997; Lui, 2009a). Academic difficulties are positively correlated with adjusting to this new culture. Students who have problems in academic areas such a teaching styles or understanding class lecturers cannot adjust to new conditions easily (Lin, 1997)

Chinese scholar Research

In the host country China international students meet a lot of stressful situations as language barriers, academic demands, homesickness, lack of social support. To cope with these stressful situations they use some stress coping strategies Stress coping is behavioral and cognitive person's efforts to respond to internal or external demands, which are perceived as exceeding his resources. Previous research established that international students use more denial, self-blame and behavioral disengagement coping strategies than domestic students. Another study by wang han showed that international students mostly used problem-oriented stress coping strategy, followed by searching for social support and behavioral disengagement strategy. Moreover, usage of stress coping strategies depends on length of time spent in the host country, and gender of student. The leading psychological problem in international students is depressive symptoms. In previous studies it was established that depressive symptoms are associated with stress coping of international students. However there is no homogenous answer, which stress coping strategies are associated with higher level of depressive symptoms.

The issues of greatest concern to international students in China are the challenges of higher education and getting used to new ways of learning and thinking, as international students come from different countries with different backgrounds (孙风格, 2016). Based on one

scholar research Zhang li (2009), international students are disparate in groups and they have different backgrounds, experience, skills, command of Chinese, English (Many university have English instruction language program) and ages. Therefore, it is true that international students in China face more difficulties to adapting to the new situation. Different people face different problems because they are from different cultures and nations (贺珊, 2013). These difficulties and problems complicate students' lives. By not considering the needs and adjustments of international students, students feeling unfulfilled, disappointed, and even exploited (Sherry, 2010).

According to one study at the University of Shanghai which is done by the international students, Abdul sami, Raheem Jafar it is founded that bigger difference between culture of students homeland and host country cause cultural stress and has the bad effect on the welfare of international students. Staying away from family, friends and cultural values, have negative impact on students cope with stress. When discriminatory attitude are added to this situation which can be considered under lack of social support, increase stress and decreases success.

Another Chinese scholar Wang li research on international students in China on the cross cultural adjustment, during the study the results shows the effects of some factors on adaption of international student in the intercultural, such as the role of acculturation strategies, self-construal's, perceived cultural distance and Chinese self-confidence. The conclusion of the study shows that it was determined that positive correlation between the above mentioned factors and lengthy period of residence in the People republic of China. Participation in the host society, direct communication, Chinese language self-confidence, marital status perceived cultural distance help in adjustment and sociocultural adjustment.

In another study conducted by one international student in China in 2011, it revealed that cultural differences was one of the most important factor affecting social adjustment of international students in China. The challenges faced by the international students in adapting the Chinese culture are complicating their adaption in their daily life and time to get the students closed to distractive level.(曲如晓., 2009) The research also revealed that the students from different culture are uncomfortable from some of behavior of Chinese who tend to ridicules when they see them in such traditional clothes. Some students misunderstood because of clothing style and accordingly express feeling of discomfort.

In 2013 research published by one Chinese scholar during his research had studied the problems faced by international students in their higher education in China and the factor that influence these problems, during his research he worked out the adaptation problems of international students and search age, gender, economic situation shelter, the host city, friends, relationship, participation in social cultural activities,

sport activities, and the nature of their training that affects social adaption. The result of his research shows that the dormitory life, Chinese speaking, loneliness and the problem caused by cultural differences are most important things that affect the international students in the education process in China(王倩., 2013). According to this result there is relation between social adoptions and the genders of students, level of income and social relationships.

A Chinese scholar found during his research psychological adjustment also significantly associated with acculturation strategy and culture distance. This also suggests the need for targeted support interventions to facilities the psychological and socio cultural adjustment of international students in the academia field(吉艳艳., 2013).

Another Chinese researcher studies result shows that the difficulties relating to cultural adaption of these students have adverse outcomes on the general adaption process while language development has no significance contribution to the process., there is no relationship between the cultural adaption and education, another point as he raised that between the cultural adaption and the language development whereas there is a connection between the language development and educational adaptation(Tang, 1996).

To summarize the major problems of international students in adaption process stem from the difficulties of cultural differences and language barrier. These socio cultural difference cause international students to have a fear of failure and feel ashamed when talking to the Chinese students, and become a discourage factor in classroom participation and social inclusion. It means that the cultural adaption problems have negative impact on the educational success rate of international students. Therefore it is necessary to attach importance to structure and implement initiatives towards tackling the adaption problems of international students along with the opportunities of accommodation and scholarship. In this regard, social work profession might take significant roles in responding the problems of international students and improving their educational success through efforts developed in cooperation with agencies in micro, and macro level. The general overview of social work practice regarding the subject matter can be found in the next section.

It is important to investigate international students' problems. Consequently, the purpose of this study is to identify categories of problems among international postgraduate students in Inner Mongolia province China.

Categories of Problems among International students in China

Categorizing the problems among international students can facilitate prevention of these problems. Studies categorized the problems facing international students. These categories are composed of several items or subsets to identify the problems among students(Al-

Zubaidi, 2009; Lebcir, 2008). Based on Sandhu (1994) two categories including Intrapersonal and interpersonal factors affect international students. Intrapersonal factors originate from the student himself and include a profound sense of loss, a sense of inferiority and a sense of uncertainty about the future. Interpersonal factors are related to the culture and environment and include communication problems, culture shock, and loss of social support. There are also some miscellaneous factors, which are not classified. These factors are differences in culture language, immigration difficulties, different educational systems and academic restrictions (Sandhu, 1994). According to Yusliza & Chelliah (2010), adjustments by students fall into two categories: Sociocultural adjustments are related to behavioral ability to fit in and can be viewed from a social learning perspective predicted by variables related to the social skills acquisitions and cognitive factors. Psychological adjustments related to anxiety depression and well-being can be understood from the stress and coping framework, as well as predicted and explained by personality and life changes and social support variables (Yusliza, 2010). Mooney & Gordon (1950), created 11 student problem categories. These categories are: Health and Physical Development, Finances, Living Conditions, and Employment, Social and Recreational Activities, Social-Psychological Relations, Marriage and Sexual Problems, Home and Family, Morals and religion (Mooney, 1950), Adjustment to College Work, The Future: Vocational and Educational, Curriculum and Teaching procedure. Al-Zubaidi and Rechards (2009) categorized international students' problems in three categories: Cultural Difficulties, Academic Difficulties and Languages Difficulties. Cultural difficulties refer to multicultural identity, including the students' religion, ethnic background, the food and lifestyle in China. Academic difficulties refer to the academic system, lecturers and methodology of teaching in China and Languages Difficulties refer to Language Laboratories, Audio Visual Material (Listening and speaking tapes, language software etc), Reference Books, Internet access (Al-Zubaidi, 2009).

Theoretical framework of Study

Based on Maslow theory, human behaviors' are motivated by a hierarchy of needs. In this theory, five requirements are inherent but the way to satisfy them is acquisitive. Need at the head of the pyramid certainly require attention more than lower needs? If people are not satisfied at one stage they will face problems in the next stage (Maslow, 1968). Students should meet their needs to increase their satisfaction and reduce their problems (Maslow, 1968). Rotter (1954), in his social learning theory, considers both internal and external issues of the organism, which means internal consolidations and the complex cognitive process and says new behaviour is shaped by observing others (Rotter, 1954). Based on Rotter's conclusion as

an individual is in the interaction with the environment he can be controlled by either internal or external factors. These two sources of control have different effects on behaviour. When one's learning is not in the line with his psychological needs, dissatisfaction will emerge (Rotter, 1954). Hence, according to Rotter students' learning conditions should be proportionate with their psychological needs. Another scholar Fromm (1990), in his Social Psychoanalytic Theory, believes that the reason for mental discomfort is disorganization in the society. He believes that sane humans grow in a sane society. In order to achieve a healthy social life for human beings, they need to come to a general agreement on certain points of view. There are adverse conditions, social life will be broken off and people cannot achieve social communication and understanding. The other need of human being is the need to appertain to somewhere. Human have fear of absolute freedom (Fromm, 1990). Therefore, humans' needs are in the society and society has been changed to accommodate human needs. Hence, Chinese Universities should accommodate students' needs.

METHOD

Participants and procedure

In this study international students were selected from a pool of graduate, postgraduate, and doctorate students (bachelor, master, and PhD level) from countries which have the highest number of students in Inner Mongolia. These countries are: Mongolia, Russia, African region, Pakistan, India, and United States of America. A random sample of 100 international students was selected from Inner Mongolia University, Inner Mongolia Normal University, Inner Mongolia Agriculture University, and Hohhot. Data from 98 students from 1st to 4th courses were approved for statistical analysis. Participants aged 18-35 years. 68% were female and 32% - male. 36 % studied language and arts 43% studied social science, and 21 % natural science. Based on Mooney Problem Check List, problems were divided into 11 categories namely: Health Problems, Financial and Lifestyle Problems, Social and Recreational Problems, Psychological Social Relations Problems, Personal Relationships and Emotional Problems, Marriage and Sexual Problems, Family Problems, Morals and Religious Problems, Academic Work Problems, Future Career Problems, Curriculum and Method of Teaching Problems.

Multi sampling was used to select the sample. First, based on stratified sampling, three countries with the highest number of students selected from 18 countries. Out of 100 students from seven countries, a total 68 students were selected based on Krejcie & Morgan (1970) sample table. Second, the questionnaires were sent to students based on systematic sampling (list of students' name). The female participants were 42% (n=28) and male participants were 58% (n=39). The

sample contains 54% (n=36) participants from Mongolia and Russia 33% (n=22) from Central Asian countries 7% (n=4) from India and 6% (n=3) from Pakistan.

International students had come to China from a lot of different countries as Asean (The association of south east Asian Nations) Mongolia, Russia, Central Asian States, Netherlands, Australia, India, Iran, Yemen, Spain, Israel, South Korea, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Poland, Lebanon, Malaise, Norway, Sweden, Vietnam, Switzerland, Turkey, United Kingdom, United States of America and Germany.

Measures

Exploratory mix method was used to measure for this research questionnaire. MPCL was used as quantitative and main method. 1st part of the questionnaire deals with demographic information and 2nd Part is situated by different items in 11 categories. The categories include Health Related Problems, Financial and Lifestyle Problems, Social and Recreational Problems, Psychological Social Relation Problems, Personal Relationships and Emotional Problems, Marriage and Sexual Problems, Family Problems, Moral and Religious Problems, Adapting to Academic Work Problems, Future Career Adapting Problems, Curriculum and Method of Teaching Problems. Reliability and validity were accepted (Cronbach alpha =0.84). As well, qualitative research approach was used in order to support the findings. The interviews were conducted with two presidents from each society. These heads were invited for interviews because they were the representatives of their countries students and they know about the problems students face. The questionnaire contained 50 items, 5 scales. Participants

were asked to evaluate how typical a given behavior was to them in stressful situation. Reliability of questionnaire was measured with Cronbach Alpha (0.5-0.93). Unreliable scales (Cronbach alpha < 0.6) such as mental disengagement, active coping and restraint were excluded from further analysis. Depressive symptoms were assessed with Zung Self-Rating Depression Scale (Zung, 1976). The scale contains 20 items. Participants were asked to choose an answer, which better suited their condition in the previous month. Reliability of the questionnaire was proved by Cronbach alpha 0.81.

Data Size

Collected data from questionnaires and survey were analyzed by using SPSS (Statistical Packages for Social Sciences). Descriptive statistic was used for Statistical Technique. The most disturbing items were found by using Pareto Principle. Pareto Principle believes that 80% of the effects come from 20% of the causes; therefore, 2-3 most disturbing items in each category were considered the disturbing problems in International students in China.

RESULT

The usage of questionnaire was compared in male and female groups of international students. Result shows that analysis confirmed that female students more often used problem and stress coping strategies such as focus on and expressing of emotions and emotional social support than male students. Other mean differences did not reach statistical significance. The graph below shows the results of questionnaire.

Graph 3: Categories of problems among international students

Further, more from the mention above categories of problems which are displayed in Graph 3 and based on Pareto Principle, 2-3 categories of problems are the most disturbing categories of problems among

international students in Inner Mongolia China. These categories of problems are regarding recreational (19%) and curriculum and teaching method (12%).

Table 1: Ratio of Category wise

Category of Social and Recreational Problems			Category of Curriculum and Method of Teaching Problems		
No.	Given response	%	No.	Given response	%
1	Lack of recreations	41.8	1	Unable to get required books	26.0
2	Lack of exercising opportunities	53.1	2	College is not concerned of students needs	43.0
3	Lack of time for art and music	61.0	3	Boring classes	29.1
4	Lack of opportunities for entertainment	59.0	4	Too many poor lecturers	39.0
5	Lack of time for myself	37.7	5	Lecturers are inefficient in teaching a certain subject	37.0
6	Inefficient use of free time	56.1	6	Lecturer has a bad personality	17.9
7	Willing to improve my thoughts	72.0	7	Lack of a good college advisor	58.0
8	Need more opportunity to express myself	61.0	8	Lack of one to one help from lecturers	43.0
9	Uncomfortable in meeting people	21.3	9	Lack of opportunity to speak to lecturers	37.0
10	Uncomfortable during dates	19.9	10	Lecturers are not interested in students	22.0
11	Late in communicating with others	27.1	11	Lecturers are not concerned about student's feelings	43.0
12	Lack of involvement in student activities	47.0	12	Lack of discussion in class	44.0
13	Boring weekends	69.6	13	Classes are as those in high schools	21.0
14	Interested in dancing	48.9	14	Lots of work and assignments	76.0
15	Interested in entertaining	89.0	15	Lecturers are too theoretical	43.0
16	Interested in changing appearance	49.9	16	Teaching is inefficient	32.0
17	Interested in improving ethics	73.0	17	Subjects are not related to course	19.0
18	Facing difficulties in continuing a conversation	37.9	18	Too many rules and regulations	37.9
19	Lack of sports skills	40.0	19	Unable to get the wanted course	32.6
20	Lack of opportunities in enjoying the environment	67.0	20	Unfair grades	29.8
21	Lack of opportunity to continue a hobby	54.1	21	Unfair tests	30.9
22	Lack of time to enjoy reading	44.2	22	Poor arrangement of campus activities	56.0
23	Interested in more discussions	79.0	23	Less lively campus	55.0
24	Lack of opportunities to enjoy own interests	56.2	24	Campus is lack of recreational facilities	65.9
25	Lack of social life	44.9	25	Long duration of classes	72.0

From all items mention in above graph 1, there are 2 categories of problems which are displayed in table 1 and according to Pareto Principle, 4-6 items are the highest disturbing items in each category. The most disturbing items in category of Social and Recreational Problems are interested in entertaining by 89%, interested to improving ethics by 73%, willing to improve my thoughts by 72.0%, interested in more discussions

by 79%, and boring weekends by 69.6%. The highest disturbing items in category of Curriculum and Method of Teaching Problems are lots of work and assignments by 76.0%, long duration of classes by 72%, campus is lack of recreational facilities by 65.0%, poor arrangement of campus activities 65%, less lively campus by 55.0%, lack of a good college advisor by 58.0% and poor arrangement of campus activities by 56%.

Interview Results

All international students mentioned that lack of announcements in Inner Mongolia's Universities is a critical issue. They do not inform about programs or information about universities. Also, students have problems with lecturer's Chinese accent; professors speak too fast which they do not get the main contents. The main problem among international students is the entertainments facilities on campus. They need more facilities for exercise and entertaining. In addition, most of the students are not satisfied with the level of teaching, and they worried that they cannot pass their

exams. The main problem among Indian and Pakistani students is lack of time. They claim that they have to do so many assignments. They also express that lecturers differentiate between local and international students, and that lecturers are not concerned about students' needs. The main problem among Russian and Mongolian students is recreational facilities such as sport facilities. They need more activities and exercise in campus.

Stress coping strategies were compared in freshmen and senior students groups in graph 4. It was ascertained that senior student compared with freshman more often used on and expressing of emotions, religious coping and less often denial.

Graph 4: Problem coping strategies in freshmen and senior international students groups

In above mention graph 3& 4 Bar a,b,c,d,e,f,g,i,j respectively shows the result of Positive reinterpretation and growth, Focus on expressing of emotions, Use of instrumental social support, Religious coping, Humor, Behavioral disengagement, Use of emotional social support, Acceptance, Suppression of competing activities, planning.

Also depressive symptoms of international students were analyzed. The results of depressive symptoms scale among international students was 28.2 7.1. Although student of natural science had higher level of depressive symptoms than the student of arts, social science, and student of language, but the result difference was statistically not significant. The same tendencies were ascertained comparing level of depressive symptoms in female and male groups. Participants were distributed into two groups by terciles. First and second terciles reflect lower level of depressive symptoms; third tercile reflects higher level of depressive symptoms.

Finally, multivariate logistic regression analysis was done to analyze associations between depressive symptoms and problem coping strategies. Analyzes revealed that problem coping explains 51% of depressive symptoms variance controlling for demographical factors such as age, gender, specialty and course ($p < 0,001$). More frequent use of such problem coping strategies as focus on and venting of emotions, behavioral disengagement, substance use and less frequent use of strategies as positive reinterpretation and humors was associated with higher level of depressive symptoms.

CONCLUSION

During the research of current subject of foreign students, China is like other developed countries shows development above becoming preferred and attractive county. In order to solve the problems of international students to ensure their participation in socio culture

activates in China and help them succeed in their education, it requires the monitoring of strategic policies to enable them to live in China.

International students consider many reasons in selecting different countries to continue their education. To study abroad all, the decision taking by the international students, culture affinity & the probability of good career after the higher education. Though the decision taken by the students, are being done willingly and expressed as step creating toward a better future, student end up encountering various problems as a result of change the country for their education. As mention in above section, the adaption problems that are experienced due to cultural differences can be described as a complex and stormy period in the life cycle of such students and this consequently worsens the condition for international students.

Since international students come from different countries, they will face different problems like other such students, international students in universities of Inner Mongolia Providence also face different problems. This study identifies different items in different categories of problems among international students in universities of Inner Mongolia. Due to the large number of items the results focus on the highest disturbing categories of problems based on Pareto Principle. Based on the result of the data gathered from questionnaire, interviews and the Pareto Principle, 2 major categories are the most disturbing. The first category is Social and Recreational Problems. Also, these finding supported with the finding of questionnaire, result of interviews and also by Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs and Fromm's Social Psychoanalytic Theory. Students require recreation to avoid from some problems such psychological problems, believe that social problems can be the source of mental health problems. The second big category of problem is Curriculum and Method of Teaching. These results are supported with findings of interview results and also Rotter's Social Learning Theory and Fromm's Social Psychoanalytic Theory. Biggs (1990), believes that Method of Teaching not only provides a „climate“ for learning, but also have motivational consequences. Therefore, curriculum is required for better collaboration among lecturers, helping them understand how their instructional decisions contribute to students' overall learning.

Cultural difference in China is one of the most critical factor affecting the success and adaption of international students during their higher studies. Therefore China, in order to have an effective strategy for international students, is expected to develop strategies in order to have to minimize cultural differences and negative effect of this issue.

Finally, results suggest to universities of Inner Mongolia providence;

Distribute literature containing necessary information about the adjustment process, educational system, banking system, counseling services, universities rules and regulations and programs such as workshops and seminars.

Universities of Inner Mongolia's province facilities should be utilized to inform all international students about Universities and their facilities.

Explore greater levels of support to enhance both students and lecturers' Chinese language ability for better communication.

Provide sports facilities such as a gym for students as well as organize short scientific trips.

Organize more relevant seminars and workshops featuring lectures by visiting professors concerning up to date technology and science to motivate students to develop new ideas. This causes teachers and students to focus on recent findings in their field and not to waste time on banal issues.

Multi-dimensional approaches and studies must be organized and conducted again the solution of these problems in different size, individual family, group, community, and resolving problems, of society and meeting the need of preventive, performing studies covering the developer converter functions. Social work profession and discipline located in size of the service and policy making determined to remove the needs of international students and solving of their problems remain significant. Most often social work practice that can be categorized micro and macro levels.

Micro level of functioning is referred to as individual based social work practice, acting with the surrounding of the individual concept made in consideration of the international student's family, friends, university, dormitory environment, identification of system that interact with students also refers to the study of these system as well.

Social work practice are performing a Marco community, service, and policy element, Young students in the society are the most dynamic element of the socio culture structure. Future professional in term of international students are young people in higher education, social investment are most important in these component. This will give many additives to international students, own country as well as the country they are educated sense. Therefore the spreading of higher education in the country next to the creation of successful policies to attract international students to the country is necessary to expand the service offered to students. In this sense, youth, international students knowing the problems faced by the international students and social workers participation in policy making process is very important.

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